

IMPROVEMENT OF AUDIT OF SETTLEMENTS WITH SUPPLIERS OF GOODS AND CONTRACTORS

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The audit of settlements with suppliers of goods and contractors plays a vital role in ensuring the financial stability and transparency of an organization. This process validates the accuracy of financial records and their compliance with regulations and internal policies. However, the increasing complexity of modern economic environments, growing transaction volumes, technological advancements, and intricate legal frameworks necessitate the continuous improvement of auditing methodologies.

Challenges in Auditing Settlements

Auditing settlements with suppliers and contractors faces several challenges. These include incomplete or inaccurate documentation, risks of errors or fraudulent activities, and difficulties in adhering to international standards. The volume and complexity of transactions in global supply chains further complicate the audit process, making traditional auditing methods less effective in addressing these issues.

Advancements in Audit Practices

The integration of advanced technologies, such as blockchain, artificial intelligence, and data analytics, has revolutionized the audit process. These tools enhance accuracy, reduce manual errors, and provide real-time insights into financial transactions. Additionally, risk-based auditing approaches prioritize high-risk areas, such as large transactions or overdue accounts, ensuring that audit resources are allocated efficiently.

Improving Internal Controls

Strengthening internal control mechanisms is essential for ensuring the integrity of settlements. This includes the implementation of automated systems for tracking invoices, purchase orders, and payments, as well as regular reconciliations to detect discrepancies early. Clear documentation practices and standardized procedures also play a critical role in enhancing audit effectiveness.

Recommendations for Improvement

To improve the audit of settlements, organizations should adopt modern technologies to automate and streamline processes. Training auditors in the use of advanced analytical tools and international standards will also enhance their

effectiveness. Furthermore, collaboration with suppliers and contractors to establish transparent communication and mutual compliance with terms will reduce risks and discrepancies.

Conclusion

The audit of settlements with suppliers and contractors is a critical aspect of financial governance. While challenges such as fraud risks, regulatory compliance, and operational inefficiencies persist, the adoption of advanced technologies and enhanced auditing frameworks provides a pathway to improvement. By focusing on innovation and strengthening internal controls, organizations can ensure the transparency, accuracy, and efficiency of their audit processes.

List of literature:

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